

Equality in Education and Culture in Surkhandarya During the Years of Independence

Hamroyeva Nodira Normurodovna

Teacher of the Department of Civil Society, Faculty of Law, TerGU

Abstract: In this article, life itself has shown that Uzbekistan, as an independent state, cannot mobilize the people to comprehensively strengthen its independence without a process of spiritual renewal in socio-political life. Therefore, from the very first days of independence, the republic's leadership took the necessary measures in this regard. In this regard, the President emphasized the need to give equal rights to all in the free choice of general secondary education, vocational training, and appropriate special training, as well as to develop and implement the New Democratic Concept.

Keywords: "On Education," "Termez," Spirituality, "Jayhun," Ideology, "Talented Children," shift.

In recent years, the process of reforms implemented in the field of education at the republican level has led to profound qualitative changes in regional public education. To carry out this noble work, special attention was paid to the widespread use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process to update the content of education. As our first President, I.A. Karimov, noted, "If the tasks of reforming the education system are successfully solved, the socio-political climate will change dramatically." Democratic values are established in front of people. A person determines their place in society.

In the 1990-2000 academic year, educational reforms were effectively continued in 778 general education schools, 19 specialized boarding schools, 3 football boarding schools, 2 sanatorium boarding schools, 2 special boarding schools, and one orphanage in the region. In the current academic year, 453,981 students received education and upbringing in existing educational institutions. In 19 boarding schools designed for working with gifted students, 3644 students were trained on an expanded program in various subjects. In his speech at the session of the Surkhandarya Regional Council of People's Deputies (March 2000), President I. Karimov noted the shortage of 1589 teachers in general education schools in the region.

The following example shows that the need for teachers in educational institutions is increasing year after year. If in 1997 this need was 1276, in 1998 - 1306, then in 1999 this figure reached 1589. Effective research is being conducted in collaboration with teachers from republican and regional schools. A number of issues related to solving the problem of providing teachers have been announced, including a resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On the need for graduates of higher educational institutions to work in their specialty for 3 years" starting from the 2004 academic year. Regional public education institutions are actively participating in republican scientific Olympiads, various competitions and competitions. At the republican science Olympiad, students of regional public education institutions took part in 17 subjects and took the 5th place. The "Ma'naviyat" group of school No. 17 in Sherabad district took first place in the republican "Kitabxon" competition. Monitoring centers have been established in many schools in

the region to popularize and implement best practices in educational institutions. Despite the fact that at the end of the 1999-2000 academic year, 41.3 million soums were allocated for the repair of general education schools, the regional administration allocated an additional 40 million soums. Sponsorship is of particular importance in supporting education and enlightenment in the region. A farmer from the Denov district, A. Narzullaev, built a two-storey school building at his own expense for 9.5 million soums. The family of N. Normuratov in the Kumkurgan district provided assistance in the amount of 700 thousand soums for the repair of the building of school No. 24 for 620 students. In the 2000 academic year, under the auspices of public education workers in the Kumkurgan district, 6 additional classrooms were built for school No. 13, and 8 additional classrooms were built for school No. 38. In accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the National Program for Personnel Training" and "On Education," as well as the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 6, 1997 "On the Fundamental Reform of the System of Education, Upbringing and Training of Personnel, Raising a Harmoniously Developed Generation." The decision of the governor of Surkhandarya region dated October 28, 1997 No. 308 was adopted. Between 1999 and 2000, certain work was carried out in the region to implement the "National Program for Personnel Training." A special staff was established to prepare 808 existing educational institutions for the 2000-2001 academic year, and plans and measures were clearly developed. It is planned to repair 89 out of 778 existing schools and 689 schools. In addition, 23 schools were provided with clean drinking water, 46 schools were gasified, 20 schools were provided with telephones and 37 schools with radios. In the 1999-2000 academic year, lessons were held in two shifts in 70 percent of the 778 general education schools, i.e., in 556.

In recent years, 33,143 teachers have worked in regional public education institutions. Of the teachers by category, 1491 (4.5%) were higher education teachers, 9110 (25.0%) were secondary education teachers, and 1361 (41.1%) were specialist teachers.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 1998 No. 4 "On improving the provision of the system of continuous education with textbooks and educational literature," certain work is being carried out in the system of public education of the region. In 2000, the number of textbooks and teaching aids stored in regional school libraries reached 5,466,000 copies. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Foreign Language Learning" of December 2012, a lot of positive work is being carried out. In 2005, at the International Folklore and Ethnographic Festival "Boysun Bahori," Kh. Khursandov's play "Kampir Topaymi Dadajan" was recognized as the winner and awarded a diploma. Also, the theater regularly organizes charity performances and concerts for the construction of the Toshguzar-Boysun-Kumkurgan railway line, border guards, soldiers, students, agricultural workers, women and youth in the city of Boisun, sanatorium for people with disabilities, Tupalang water reservoir and hydroelectric power station. The theater team frequently visits enterprises and organizations, organizes round tables, meetings and concerts, promotes decrees and orders of the government. Today, 106 artists and workers are working productively in the collective. Their humble services have been well appreciated by our people and government. Two members of the team were awarded the honorary titles of "People's Artist of Uzbekistan," one - "Artist of Uzbekistan," eight - "Honored Artist of Uzbekistan," and one - "Honored Cultural Worker of Uzbekistan."

A large group of active members of the team were awarded the orders and medals of Uzbekistan. The team is busy with modest work for the sake of goodness and earns the respect of our people. Also, many folk dramas and puppet theaters operate in the districts of the region. These are the folk drama theater at the Termez city house of culture, which received the "People's Title" in 1960;

In conclusion, it should be noted that during the years of independence, great changes have taken place in the system of public education in Uzbekistan, which plays an important role in raising a comprehensively developed generation in our country.

List of literature

1. Ражабов Қ.Хасанов Ф. Қандов Б.Ўзбекистон республикасининг мустақиллик солномаси.Т."Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси".2011.-Б.53.
2. Ғуломов С. Убайдуллаева Р. Аҳмедов Э. Мустақил Ўзбекистон.Т."Ислом университети".2003.-Б.114.
3. Турсунов С.Қобилов Э.Муртазоев Б. Пардаев Т. Сурхондарё тарихи.Т."Шарқ".2004.-Б.526.
4. Турсунов С.Қобилов Э.Муртазоев Б. Пардаев Т. Сурхондарё тарихи.Т."Шарқ".2004.-Б.526.
5. Yusupovich, Koshakov Safarali. "Material Culture in Zoroastian Religion." *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521) 2.6 (2024): 715-719.
6. Isayev, Oybek. "THE ORGANIZATION OF A ZOO IN THE CITY OF TERMIZ, SOUTHERN REGION OF UZBEKISTAN." *Interpretation and researches* (2024).
7. Isayev, Oybek. "THE CULTURAL LIFE IN SURKHAN OASIS: INFORMING OF ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROBLEMS BASED ON ARCHIVAL MATERIALS (1925–1941 YEARS)." *The Light of Islam* 2019.4 (2019): 31.
8. Qudratov, Namoz, and Oybek Isayev. "DENOVO BOZORI FAOLIYATI 1946-1961-YILLAR." *Talqin va tadqiqotlar* (2024).
9. Oybek, PhD Isaev. "In the Study of the History of Surkhandarya in the 30s of the XX Century, as a Historical Source." *Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics* 7 (2022): 100-102.
10. Исаев, Ойбек Ахмед. "Освещение проблем образования Сурханского оазиса в архивных материалах (1920-1930 гг.)." *Бюллетень науки и практики* 6.8 (2020): 289-294.
11. Yusupovich, Koshakov Safarali. "Material Culture in Zoroastian Religion." *Excellencia: International Multi-disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521) 2.6 (2024): 715-719.
12. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИДА ДАФН МАРОСИМЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ." *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH* 3 (2023): 201-208.
13. Yusupovich, Koshakov Safarali. "THE ROLE OF ANCIENT BACTERIA AND MARGIA IN THE ESTABLISHMENT OF ZARDUSTIYA." *Chief Editor* 12.
14. Бабаева, Ситора Рuzimahmatovна. "Взгляд на историю топливно-энергетического комплекса Сурханского оазиса." *Бюллетень науки и практики* 7.2 (2021): 394-397.
15. Boboeva, Sitora Ruzimahmatovна. "HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE FUEL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN." *World Economics and Finance Bulletin* 4 (2021): 6-8.
16. Бобоева, С. Р. "Исторические топонимы вдоль торгового пути Термез-«Железные ворота»." *Бюллетень науки и практики* 6.2 (2020): 347-355.
17. Бобоева, Ситора. "БОЙСУН ТАРИХИЙ ТОПОНИМИ ҲАҚИДА." *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ* 21 (2019).
18. Sitora Ruzimahmatova Boboeva. (2023). THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF ELECTRIC NETWORKS IN THE SURKHAN OASIS. (USING THE EXAMPLE OF 1914-1941). *Scientific Impulse*, 2(13), 300–306.
19. Kultaeva, Fazilat. "Study of ergonyms in uzbeki linguistics." *World Bulletin of Social Sciences* 16 (2022): 11-14.

20. Kultayeva, Fazilat. "Ergonimlarning jahon va o'zbek tilshunosligida o'rganilishi." E Conference Zone. 2022.
21. KULTAEVA, Fazilat. "Analysis of ergonomic units at the onomastic level." (2022).
22. Bakhtiyorovna, Kultayeva Fazilat. "Production Characteristics of Ergonomics." American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769) 1.10 (2023): 666-670.
23. Fazilat, Kultayeva. "ERGONIMLARNI MA'NOVIY VA VAZIFAVIY KLASSIFIKATSIYALASH XUSUSIDA." «CONTEMPORARY TECHNOLOGIES OF COMPUTATIONAL LINGUISTICS» 2.22.04 (2024): 556-560.
24. Fazilat, Kultayeva. "FANDA ERGONIMLARNING O'RGANILISHI XUSUSIDA." Philological research: language, literature, education 2.2 (2024).